

Analysis of Price Perception and Celebrity Endorser on Purchasing Decisions for Skintific Skincare Products of UNRI Gen Z Graduate Students with Intervening Variables Online Customer Review

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to determine Analysis of Price Perception and Celebrity Endorser on Purchasing Decisions for Skintific Skincare Products of UNRI Gen Z Graduate Students with Intervening Variables Online Customer Review. The study was conducted by distributing questionnaires to 210 active postgraduate students at the University of Riau born between 1996 and 2010. The results of this study indicate that Celebrity Endorser, Online Customer Review, and price perception have a positive effect on purchasing decisions. Celebrity Endorser and price perception have a positive effect on Online Customer Review. Online Customer Review significantly mediates the relationship between Celebrity Endorser and purchasing decisions. Online Customer Review significantly mediates the relationship between price perception and purchasing decisions.

INTRODUCTION

In the current era of globalization, the business world continues to experience rapid development and competition, including the cosmetic industry in Indonesia. Based on data from the National Industrial Information System (2022), cosmetics are one of the three national priority industries in accordance with the National Industrial Development Master Plan (RIPIN) 2015-2035.

The results of the ZAP Beauty Index 2023 survey show that 76.4% of Indonesian women use skincare for skin brightening benefits. The protective benefits of UV rays were chosen by 60% of respondents, and 80.2% of Gen Xers sought anti-aging benefits. Generation Z focuses on the benefits of brightening (77.4%) and camouflaging acne scars (60.7%). Product safety is the main factor for 79.6% of Indonesian women in choosing skincare, while affordability is considered by 61% of respondents, higher than influencer reviews which are only chosen by 27%.

One of the most popular skincare products is a moisturizer from Skintific, a Canadian brand that was first marketed in 1957 in Oslo, Norway, and is now produced by scientists in Canada. Skintific uses Trilogy Triangle Effect (TTE) technology to overcome skin barrier problems and is safe for sensitive skin. In 2023, Skintific

occupies the first position of the top serum brand with the highest revenue of IDR 18.7 billion as of January 2023.

Skintific won seven prestigious awards in the span of one year, including "Best Moisturizer." Their products such as 5x Ceramide Moisturizer and Mugwort Acne Clay Stick went viral, placing Skintific as the TOP 1 Beauty Category on various e-commerce platforms in Indonesia such as Shopee and Tokopedia. However, the distribution of this product is limited to the Pekanbaru area, only available at a few local cosmetic counters and not in public supermarkets.

Compass Dashboard data shows the high trend of online shopping for beauty products in Pekanbaru, with many purchases made through e-commerce platforms. It is important to understand the dynamics and preferences of consumers in the purchase of beauty products in this region, specifically the shift from physical to online stores. Products such as Makeover, Wardah, and Maybelline are the top choices of consumers in local cosmetic stores. According to employees at Guardian and Century, buyers of Skintific products are mostly women under 30 years old, the Gen Z category. Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) in 2020, the number of Gen Z residents in Pekanbaru reached 248,876 people, with many of them being students of Riau University.

The purchase decision of skincare products involves several important factors: product features and quality, time of purchase, choice of dealer, number of purchases, and payment method. Early surveys of Skintific product purchase decisions show that product variants, evaluations of other brands, availability in various stores, and modern payment methods are important factors for consumers.

Online Customer Review (OCR) is an important factor in purchasing decisions in e-commerce. Reviews from customers on social media greatly influence consumer purchase intent. Research shows that the quality and quantity of reviews, as well as the credibility of the source, have a positive relationship to purchase intent.

Price is also a significant factor in purchasing decisions for skincare products. Affordable prices and in accordance with the quality of the product influence the purchase decision. Skintific products, which fall into the middle to upper price category, offer quality and benefits that match the price tag, supporting consumer purchasing decisions.

Using celebrities as endorsers on social media like TikTok increases consumers' trust in brands, making them more confident to buy. Testimonials from respected celebrities increase the appeal of the product. This strategy influences purchasing decisions positively, as Skintific did with celebrities like Tasya Farasya and Nicholas Saputra.

Research shows a positive relationship between independent variables such as celebrity endorsers, price, and OCR on beauty product purchase decisions. However, some studies show differences in results, suggesting a research gap. Therefore, further research needs to be done on price perception, celebrity endorsers, and OCR as mediating variables for purchasing decisions for Skintific products by UNRI Generation Z graduate students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Price Perception

Consumers are individuals with different characteristics. The assessment felt by each consumer on a product or service they receive is not the same. Consumer perception of a price can influence decisions in buying a product so that a company must be able to provide a good perception of the products or services they sell (Lina, 2023).

According to Asnori (2020), perception is one of the terms used in the field of psychology. In general, the definition of perception is defined as a direct response or the process of a person knowing some things through the senses. While in the large dictionary of psychology, perception is defined as a process of observing a person to the environment using the senses possessed so that he becomes aware of everything in his environment.

Tjiptono and Diana (2016), formulated the definition of price as the overall sacrifice that consumers are willing to make in order to obtain a specific product or service. Price is a component that directly affects the company. The set price level affects the quality sold. In addition, price can indirectly affect costs because the quantity sold affects the costs incurred in relation to production efficiency.

B. Celebrity Endorser

According to Cuomo et.al., (2019) A celebrity endorser is someone known and has many followers on social media that companies use to introduce and influence consumers to use the product. This person is an artist, entertainer, blogger, vlogger, celebgram, athlete, and influencer who is widely known for his success in the field he pursues (Riani et.al., 2023).

Celebrity endorser is the use of certain celebrities or figures who have the expertise to introduce products so that they are more easily recognized and can increase effectiveness so that they can attract consumers to buy the product (Christiana & Lubis, 2023)

C. Online Customer Review (OCR)

OCR is a positive or negative statement made by a potential, current, or former customer about a product or company that is available to many people or institutions over the internet. OCR is a form of WOM (Word of Mouth) in online sales that makes prospective buyers get information about products from consumers who have made purchases and benefit from the product (Fileri, 2014).

OCR is a tool used by consumers to find and obtain information that will later be able to attract interest and influence purchasing decisions. OCR is also interpreted as positive or negative reviews of products that have been sold in online shops or can also be referred to as an evaluation of information from goods and services created by consumers (Ardianti and Widiartanto, 2019).

D. Purchase Decision

Kevin & Saputra (2022), purchasing decision is an assessment or thinking process carried out by consumers by combining knowledge about the products being compared and finally deciding on one consumer's final choice.

Purchasing decisions are part of consumer behavior consumer behavior is the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations choose, buy, use, and how goods, services, ideas or experiences to satisfy their needs and desires. A purchase decision is a decision to continue or not continue a purchase. The purchase decision will be based on a fairly well-known brand. Purchase decisions occur when consumers will make purchases and are interested in brands that are their favorites where there are two factors, namely purchase intention and purchase decision (Rahmawati et.. al., 2022).

E. Generation Z

Generation Z, also commonly referred to as Gen Z, is a demographic group born between mid-1996 and early 2010s. They are the next generation of Generation Y or Millennials and have unique characteristics that set them apart from previous generations. Generation Z is the product of rapid technological development, social changes, and historical events that affect their development. (Suryathi et.al., 2023).

One major characteristic of Generation Z is that they are: The first generation born and raised in the digital age. They grew up with technologies such as the internet, smart phones, social media, and easy access to information. As a result, Generation Z has a high level of digital literacy and the ability to use technology quickly and effectively. They are often considered "digital natives" because they have been accustomed to digital devices from an early age (Wijayanto, 2019).

Generation Z, including the group that regularly does online shopping, has a tendency to buy fashion products as their main list, followed by skin care products. The main reason they buy these products even though they can be purchased offline is the discount they receive if they make purchases through online media, in addition to cheaper prices, their tendency to prefer convenience makes them prefer to buy through smartphones that already have many product variants rather than having to go around one store to another. This Generation Z considers that going around from one store to another wastes their time, and of course their money (Hemastuti et.al., 2022).

G. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source : *Teori Penerimaan Teknologi (TAM)* (Sabira et.al., 2022), *Economic Theory (Price)* (Rafa et.al., 2023), *Endorser Credibility Theory* (Putrianianda, 2023)

HYPOTHESIS

- H1: It is suspected that price perception has a significant effect on OCR
- H2: It is suspected that Celebrity endorsers allegedly have a significant effect on OCR
- H3: It is suspected that Price Perception has an effect on purchasing decisions
- H4: It is suspected that Celebrity endorsers have an effect on purchasing decisions
- H5: It is suspected that Online Customer Review as an intervening variable has an effect on purchasing decisions
- H6: It is suspected that price perception through the variable Online Customer Review has an effect on purchasing decisions
- H7: It is suspected that Celebrity Endorser through the Online Customer Review variable has an effect on purchasing decisions.

METHOD

This research was conducted from 2023 to 2024, with questionnaires distributed to Gen Z postgraduate students at UNRI. Out of the distributed questionnaires, 210 respondents participated, each responding to 41 statements. The sampling method used was non-probability sampling, specifically purposive sampling. Respondents were selected based on the following criteria: Active postgraduate students at Universitas Riau, Born between 1996 and 2010 (Generation Z), Have previously purchased Skintific skincare products and actively use the internet, social media, and online forums to search for and read reviews about Skintific products.

The results obtained were analyzed using the Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) method, utilizing SmartPLS 4 software. SEM-PLS can perform analysis in one test and explain the relationship between variables. PLS is used to assist researchers in supporting theories and explaining whether there is a relationship between latent variables or not. The PLS method is capable of describing latent variables (not directly measured) and is measured using indicators (Ghozali and Latan, 2020). SEM-PLS was chosen because this research has latent variables that can be measured based on indicators, allowing the author to conduct analysis with clear and detailed calculations. The variables used in this study are described as follows:

Table 1.1 Variabel Operational Definition

Variables	Definition	Dimensions	Indicator	Scale
Purchase Decision (Y)	The process of judgment or thinking that consumers do by combining knowledge	Information Research	1. Product Choice	Ordinal
		Evaluation of alternatives	2. Brand Choice	
			3. Choice of distributor	

	about the products being compared and finally deciding on one final consumer choice.	Purchase decision Alma (2018)	4. Purchase Time 5. Purchase Quantity 6. Payment Method Kotler & Amstrong (2016:57)	
Online Customer Review (Z)	Positive or negative statements made by potential, current, or former customers about a product or company that are available to many people or institutions via the internet.	Credible, trustworthy and honest	1. Source credibility 2. Argument quality Dzulqarnain (2019) 3. Review Timelines Cheong <i>et.al.</i> , (2019)	Ordinal
		Expertise and usefulness	4. Perceived Usefulness 5. Quantity of reviews Dzulqarnain (2019)	
		Fun, interesting and likely to buy Megawati (2018)	6. Review Valence Cheong <i>et.al.</i> , (2019)	
Price Perception (X1)	A person's ability in assessing an item with a unit of measuring instrument rupiah to be able to buy the product offered	Perceived Quality	1. Price compatibility with product quality 2. Price in accordance with the benefits	Ordinal
		Perception of costs incurred (Harjati dan Vanesia (2015:67)	3. Affordable product price 4. Price according to ability or price competitiveness. (Kotler & Amstrong, 2016)	
Celebrity endorser (X2)	Celebrity endorser is someone who is known and has many followers on social media.	Trust	1. Trustworthiness	Ordinal
		Expertise	2. Expertise 3. Respect	
		Attractiveness Shimp (2014:470)	1. Attractiveness 2. Similarity Shimp (2014:470)	

Source: Processed Data (2024)

The data obtained from this study were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) via SMART/PLS software. SEM combines factor analysis and multivariate regression to examine relationships between variables, while PLS shifts from covariance-based to variance-based SEM. This approach simplifies the investigation of various variables' simultaneous effects and tests both direct and indirect effects of independent variables on dependent variables.

The analysis includes outer model testing to ensure validity and reliability. Validity assessment involves testing convergent validity (Loading Factor, Average Variance Extracted) and discriminant validity (Cross Loading, Fornell-Larcker). Reliability is assessed through Composite Reliability and Cronbach's alpha, following guidelines by Hair et al. (2014).

Inner model testing examines relationships between latent constructs using R-square and Model Fit tests. The R-square test categorizes influence levels between variables, while Model Fit is evaluated using the Normed Fit Index (NFI). Hypothesis testing evaluates path coefficient estimates through bootstrapping,

considering relationships significant if the t-statistic exceeds 1.96 (5% significance) or 1.65 (10% significance). Hypotheses are accepted if $P < 0.05$.

For testing in this study, used:

Outer Model

1. Convergent Validity Results

Refers to the extent to which latent variables correlate with their indicators. It is expected that the value of the loading factor > 0.7 .

2. Discriminant Validity Results

Discriminant validity can be tested by comparing the intended construct value with other construct values, ensuring cross-loading values from various factors. The value of the intended construct must be higher than all others for sufficient discriminant validity. Composite reliability indicates how reliable a structure is; Values above 0.7 indicate high reliability.

3. Composite Reliability Results

Composite reliability which is a measurement with criteria if the value obtained is > 0.7 , then the construct value has high reliability.

4. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) which is the average value of variance with a minimum value of 0.5.

5. Cronbach Alpha

Cronbach's alpha calculation serves as a tool to demonstrate composite reliability results, with a minimum threshold of 0.6.

Inner Model

6. Coefficient of determination / R-Square (R^2)

The R-Square shows how much influence between variables in the model. The scores are divided into three categories: low (1-40%), medium (41-70%), and high (71-100%).

7. Predictive relevance (Q^2)

The Predictive relevance (Q^2) is a test performed to validate the model. The value of Q^2 that must be owned is > 0 so that the model shows the resulting observation value is good. If $Q^2 < 0$, the model shows that the resulting observation value is not good.

8. Model Fit

Model Fit is a test conducted to see how well the model under study by looking at the results on the NFI (Normed Fix Index). The NFI value indicates what percentage of the model studied is fit. The closer the value to 1, the better.

9. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing is done by looking at path coefficients through bootstrapping. Significant value if t-statistic > 1.96 (significance 5%) or > 1.65 (significance 10%). The alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted if $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Outer Model Evaluation Results

a. Convergent Validity Testing based on Outer Loading

Tabel 2. Outer Loading

	Celebrity Endorser (X2)	Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	Online Customer Review (Z)	Persepsi Harga (X1)
CE1	0,921			
CE10	0,711			
CE2	0,891			
CE3	0,906			
CE4	0,889			
CE5	0,875			

CE6	0,855
CE7	0,863
CE8	0,920
CE9	0,780
KP1	0,790
KP10	0,847
KP11	0,858
KP12	0,835
KP2	0,776
KP3	0,807
KP4	0,856
KP5	0,885
KP6	0,833
KP7	0,723
KP8	0,738
KP9	0,824
OCR1	0,867
OCR10	0,729
OCR11	0,745
OCR12	0,785
OCR2	0,889
OCR3	0,799
OCR4	0,828
OCR5	0,801
OCR6	0,882
OCR7	0,834
OCR8	0,800
OCR9	0,857
PH1	0,787
PH2	0,910
PH3	0,923
PH4	0,780
PH5	0,929
PH6	0,770

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Figure 2. Outer Loading

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on the outer loading validity test in Table 4.2 and Figure 4.1, it is known that all outer loading values > 0.7, which means that they have met the validity requirements based on outer loading value.

2. Discriminant Validity Testing: Cross-Loading

Tabel 3. Discriminant Validity-Cross Loading

	Celebrity Endorser (X2)	Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	Online Customer Review (Z)	Persepsi Harga (X1)
CE1	0,921	0,582	0,538	0,407
CE10	0,711	0,290	0,331	0,236
CE2	0,891	0,579	0,485	0,315
CE3	0,906	0,499	0,473	0,330
CE4	0,889	0,503	0,460	0,289
CE5	0,875	0,628	0,621	0,382
CE6	0,855	0,635	0,575	0,326
CE7	0,863	0,414	0,389	0,240
CE8	0,920	0,521	0,512	0,347
CE9	0,780	0,324	0,288	0,173
KP1	0,380	0,790	0,654	0,456
KP10	0,520	0,847	0,667	0,526
KP11	0,585	0,858	0,709	0,502
KP12	0,413	0,835	0,672	0,416
KP2	0,468	0,776	0,580	0,451

KP3	0,517	0,807	0,627	0,467
KP4	0,599	0,856	0,736	0,537
KP5	0,479	0,885	0,764	0,558
KP6	0,364	0,833	0,716	0,498
KP7	0,515	0,723	0,581	0,507
KP8	0,493	0,738	0,540	0,418
KP9	0,524	0,824	0,695	0,510
OCR1	0,418	0,732	0,867	0,345
OCR10	0,533	0,616	0,729	0,457
OCR11	0,483	0,576	0,745	0,307
OCR12	0,466	0,605	0,785	0,431
OCR2	0,416	0,732	0,889	0,432
OCR3	0,518	0,714	0,799	0,499
OCR4	0,409	0,702	0,828	0,382
OCR5	0,348	0,606	0,801	0,347
OCR6	0,479	0,704	0,882	0,404
OCR7	0,446	0,655	0,834	0,422
OCR8	0,493	0,639	0,800	0,445
OCR9	0,490	0,707	0,857	0,417
PH1	0,386	0,449	0,358	0,787
PH2	0,302	0,541	0,432	0,910
PH3	0,370	0,602	0,483	0,923
PH4	0,172	0,381	0,310	0,780
PH5	0,336	0,567	0,475	0,929
PH6	0,274	0,482	0,461	0,770

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on the data from the table, it can be seen that all indicators have met discriminant validity. The Celebrity Endorser (X2) variable has 10 indicators denoted by CE1 to CE10. The CE1 indicator has a loading value of 0.921, which is greater than the loading values to other constructs, namely 0.582, 0.538, and 0.407. Similarly, other indicators also show higher loading values compared to other constructs. For instance, CE2 has a loading value of 0.891, which is greater than 0.579, 0.485, and 0.315.

The Purchase Decision (Y) variable has 12 indicators denoted by KP1 to KP12. The KP1 indicator has a loading value of 0.790, which is greater than the loading values to other constructs, namely 0.654, 0.456, and 0.380. Other indicators also follow this pattern, such as KP10, which has a loading value of 0.847, higher than 0.667, 0.526, and 0.520.

The Online Customer Review (Z) variable has 12 indicators denoted by OCR1 to OCR12. The OCR1 indicator has a loading value of 0.867, which is higher than the loading values to other constructs, namely 0.732, 0.345, and 0.418. Similarly, OCR2 has a loading value of 0.889, which is greater than 0.732, 0.432, and 0.416.

The Price Perception (X1) variable has 6 indicators denoted by PH1 to PH6. The PH1 indicator has a loading value of 0.787, which is greater than the loading values to other constructs, namely 0.449, 0.358, and 0.386. Other indicators, such as PH2, also show higher loading values, with 0.910 compared to 0.541, 0.432, and 0.302.

Overall, each indicator within its respective construct has a higher loading value compared to other constructs, ensuring discriminant validity.

Tabel 4. Validitas Diskriminan: Fornell & Larcker

	Celebrity Endorser (X2)	Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	Online Customer Review (Z)	Persepsi Harga (X1)
Celebrity Endorser (X2)	(0,863)			
Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0,600	(0,816)		
Online Customer Review (Z)	0,561	0,815	(0,820)	
Persepsi Harga (X1)	0,365	0,599	0,500	(0,853)

Source: Processed Data, 2024

In discriminant validity testing, the AVE square root value of a latent variable is compared with the correlation value between that latent variable and other latent variables. It is known that the square root value of AVE for each latent variable is greater than the correlation value between the latent variable and other latent variables. So it is concluded that it has met the requirements for discriminant validity.

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Tabel 5. Validitas Diskriminan: HTMT

	Celebrity Endorser (X2)	Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	Online Customer Review (Z)
Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0,601		
Online Customer Review (Z)	0,564	0,849	
Persepsi Harga (X1)	0,371	0,630	0,523

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on the results of discriminant validity testing with the HTMT approach, it is known that all values < 0.9, which means that it is concluded that it has met the discriminant validity requirements based on the HTMT approach.

3. Composite Reliability (CR)

Tabel 6. Composite Reliability

	Composite Reliability
Celebrity Endorser (X2)	0,967
Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0,960
Online Customer Review (Z)	0,961
Persepsi Harga (X1)	0,941

Sumber: Lampiran 5. Data Hasil Olahan, 2024

The recommended CR value is above 0.7. It is known that all CR values > 0.7, which means that it has met the reliability requirements based on CR

4. Validity Testing based on Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Tabel 7. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variabel	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Celebrity Endorser (X2)	0,745
Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0,665
Online Customer Review (Z)	0,672

Persepsi Harga (X1)

0,727

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Celebrity endorser variables, price perception, OCR and purchase decisions result in an AVE value of >0.5 (Mahfut & Rahmono, 2021). That is, a single latent variable can account for more than half of its indicator variance, and an indicator that calculates that variable is considered valid because it can demonstrate acceptable convergent validity.

5. Cronbach's Alpha (CA)

Tabel 8. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

	Cronbach's Alpha
Celebrity Endorser (X2)	0,962
Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0,954
Online Customer Review (Z)	0,955
Persepsi Harga (X1)	0,923

Source: Processed Data, 2024

The recommended CA value is above 0.7. It is known that all CA values > 0.7, which means that it has met the reliability requirements based on Cronbach's alpha.

6. R-Square (R^2)

Tabel 9. R-Square

	R Square
Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0,736
Online Customer Review (Z)	0,415

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on the table The R-Square value of the Purchase Decision (Y) is 0.736, which means that Price Perception (X1), Celebrity Endorser (X2), Online Customer Review (Z) are able to explain or influence the Purchase Decision (Y) by 73.6%, the remaining 26.4% is influenced by other factors.

The R-Square value of Online Customer Review (Z) is 0.415, which means Price Perception (X1), Celebrity Endorser (X2) is able to explain or influence Online Customer Review (Z) by 41.5%, the remaining 58.5% is influenced by other factors.

7. Predictive relevance (Q^2)

Tabel 10. R-Square

	$Q^2 (=1-SSE/SSO)$
Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0,478
Online Customer Review (Z)	0,267

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on the data Q-Square (Q^2) value of the Purchase Decision (Y) is $0.478 > 0$, which means Price Perception (X1), Celebrity Endorser (X2), OCR (Z) have predictive relevance to the Purchase Decision (Y). The Q-Square (Q^2) value of OCR (Z) is $0.267 > 0$, which means Price Perception (X1), Celebrity Endorser (X2) has predictive relevance to OCR (Z).

Tabel 11. F-Square

	Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	Online Customer Review (Z)
Celebrity Endorser (X2)	0,081	0,283
Online Customer Review (Z)	0,789	
Persepsi Harga (X1)	0,155	0,172

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Based on the data the F-Square Celebrity Endorser (X2) value to Purchase Decision (Y) is 0.081, indicating moderate influence. F-Square Online Customer Review (Z) value to Purchase Decision (Y) is 0.789, indicating a strong influence. F-Square value of Price Perception (X1) to Purchase Decision (Y) is 0.155, indicating a strong influence. F-Square Celebrity Endorser (X2) score against Online Customer Review (Z) is 0.283, indicating a strong influence. Price perception F-square value (X1). The F-Square value of Price Perception (X1) against Online Customer Review (Z) is 0.172, indicating a strong influence.

8. Model Fit

Tabel 12. F-Square

	Estimated Model
SRMR	0,080

Source: Processed Data, 2024

The Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) value is used to match the relationship between variables in the observed model. The model is considered feasible to explain the relationship between these variables if the SRMR value < 0.08 or can be tolerated up to < 0.1 (Hardisman, 2021). It is known that based on the results of the goodness of fit SRMR test, the value of $SRMR = 0.080 < 0.1$, it is concluded that the model has been FIT.

9. Hypothesis Testing

Structural analysis or hypothesis testing aims at evaluating the statistical significance of the developed model, assessing whether the relationship between exogenous (independent) and endogenous (dependent) variables is significant. The relationship between variables is considered significant if the T test > 1.96 and P-Values < 0.05 with a significance level of 5% in two-way testing (Hardisman, 2021).

Tabel 13. Hypothesis Testing Results (direct effect)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Celebrity Endorser (X2) -> Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0,178	0,175	0,071	2,516	0,012
Celebrity Endorser (X2) -> Online Customer Review (Z)	0,437	0,430	0,085	5,121	0,000
Online Customer Review (Z) -> Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0,598	0,599	0,097	6,181	0,000
Persepsi Harga (X1) -> Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0,236	0,235	0,068	3,464	0,001
Persepsi Harga (X1) -> Online Customer Review (Z)	0,340	0,341	0,084	4,065	0,000

Source: Processed Data, 2024

Tabel 14. Hypothesis Testing Results (indirect effect)

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Persepsi Harga (X1) -> Online Customer Review (Z) -> Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0,203	0,206	0,066	3,086	0,002
Celebrity Endorser (X2) -> Online Customer Review (Z) -> Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	0,261	0,260	0,075	3,501	0,001

Source: Processed Data, 2024

DISCUSSION

The Effect of Price Perception on Online Customer Reviews

H1: It is suspected that price perception has a significant effect on OCR

Price perception is a crucial factor influencing consumer purchasing decisions, especially in e-commerce. It affects both purchase decisions and post-purchase reviews. The study found a P-Value of 0.034 (Table 4.21), indicating a significant impact of price perception on online customer reviews (OCR), as $0.034 < 0.05$. This means a positive price perception leads to better reviews, showing a significant relationship between price perception and OCR.

The effect size of price perception on OCR is 0.268, indicating a moderate impact (Babin et al., 2014). Consumers who feel the price is fair or lower than expected tend to leave positive reviews. Conversely, if they feel the price is too high, they leave negative reviews. The highest average score for price perception is 3.86 for the indicator "The product price matches the quality provided." The lowest average score is for "The product price is cheaper compared to similar products on the market," indicating many consumers don't feel the price is cheaper than competitors.

The Influence of Celebrity Endorsers on Online Customer Reviews

H2: It is suspected that Celebrity endorsers allegedly have a significant effect on OCR

Celebrity Endorser (X2) has a positive effect on Online Customer Review (OCR), with a coefficient value (Original Sample column) = 0.437, and significant, with T-Statistics = 5.121 > 1.96, and P-Values = 0.000 < 0.05. That is, the hypothesis is accepted that there is a significant influence of celebrity endorsers on OCR. The value of the Celebrity Endorser variable effect size on OCR is 0.283, indicating that the influence of celebrity endorsers on OCR is strong or large.

When consumers feel that celebrities who endorse the product have credibility and relevance, they tend to give more positive reviews. Celebrity endorsers play an important role in increasing consumer confidence in the product, which is then reflected in positive reviews. Consumers who see celebrities they admire endorse a product tend to feel more confident in making purchases and leaving good reviews. This suggests that online reviews from other users, endorsed by celebrity endorsers, have a significant influence on consumers' purchasing decisions, as they are perceived as more objective and reliable.

The Effect of Price Perception on Purchasing Decisions

H3: It is suspected that Price Perception has an effect on purchasing decisions

There is an influence of price perception variables on purchasing decision variables with coefficient values (Original Sample column) = 0.236, and significant, with T-Statistics = 3.464 > 1.96, and P-Values = 0.001 < 0.05. That is, the hypothesis is accepted that there is a significant influence of price perception on purchasing decisions. This shows that affordable prices and appropriate quality provided by Skintific on Tiktok Shop can strengthen the decision of potential customers to buy products Skintific.

The value of the Effect size variable Price Perception on Purchasing Decisions is 0.155, indicating that the influence of price perception on purchasing decisions is strong or large. The role of price perception in shaping consumer purchasing decisions has been the focus of significant research within the field of marketing. Consumers tend to make purchasing decisions when they feel that the price paid is proportional to the value received.

The Influence of Celebrity Endorsers on Purchasing Decisions

H4: It is suspected that Celebrity endorsers have an effect on purchasing decisions

There is an influence of the Celebrity Endorser variable (X2) on the Purchase Decision variable (Y) of UNRI Gen Z graduate students with a coefficient value (Original Sample column) = 0.236, and significant, with T-Statistics = 3.464 > 1.96, and P-Values = 0.001 < 0.05. That is, the hypothesis is accepted that there is a significant influence of celebrity endorsers on purchasing decisions. This shows that the use of the right celebrity endorser can strengthen a potential customer's decision to buy product Skintific. The value of the Effect size of the Celebrity Endorser variable on Purchase Decisions is 0.236, indicating that the influence of celebrity endorsers on purchasing decisions is strong or large.

This condition is seen when consumers feel that the celebrity who endorses the product has credibility and relevance, they are more likely to make a purchase decision. This proves that celebrity endorsers have a

positive impact on the sales of a product because consumers feel interested and curious about the product after seeing their favorite celebs convey product messages well so they decide to buy their products (Mamahit et al., 2022).

The Influence of Online Customer Reviews on Purchasing Decisions

H5: It is suspected that Online Customer Review as an intervening variable has an effect on purchasing decisions

There is an influence of Online Customer Review (Z) variables on the Purchasing Decisions (Y) of UNRI Gen Z graduate students. OCR has a positive effect on purchasing decisions with coefficient values (Original Sample column) = 0.598, and significant, with T-Statistics = 6.181 > 1.96, and P-Values = 0.000 < 0.05. That is, the hypothesis is accepted that there is a significant influence of OCR on purchasing decisions. These results suggest that positive online customer reviews can improve consumer purchasing decisions towards products.

The value of the OCR variable effect size on purchasing decisions is 0.598, indicating that the influence of OCR on purchasing decisions is strong or large (Babin et al., 2014). This condition is seen when consumers feel that reviews provided by other customers are trustworthy and relevant, they tend to make purchasing decisions

The Effect of Price Perception on Purchasing Decisions through Online Customer Reviews

H6: It is suspected that price perception through the variable Online Customer Review has an effect on purchasing decisions

Based on data it can be seen that OCR (Z) significantly mediates the relationship between Price Perception (X1) and Purchase Decision (Y), with T-Statistics = 3.086 > 1.96, and P-Values = 0.002 < 0.05. Thus the hypothesis of mediation is accepted. Thus, there is a significant and positive influence obtained by price perception on purchasing decisions. OCR (Z) significantly mediates the relationship between Price Perception (X1) and Purchase Decision (Y).

The value of the Effect size variable Price Perception on Purchase Decisions through OCR shows that good price perception can strengthen online customer reviews in influencing purchase decisions. Companies in creating prices must think about the perception of prices from consumers for their products. A product with a price that matches the benefits needed by consumers will cause a positive price perception for the company

The Influence of Celebrity Endorsers on Purchasing Decisions through Online Customer Reviews

H7: It is suspected that Celebrity Endorser through the Online Customer Review variable has an effect on purchasing decisions.

There is an influence of the Celebrity Endorser variable (X2) on the Purchase Decision variable (Y) of UNRI Gen Z graduate students with a coefficient value (Original Sample column) = 0.236, and significant, with T-Statistics = 3.464 > 1.96, and P-Values = 0.001 < 0.05. That is, the hypothesis is accepted that there is a significant influence of celebrity endorsers on purchasing decisions. This shows that the use of the right celebrity endorser can strengthen a potential customer's decision to buy product Skintific.

The value of the Effect size of the Celebrity Endorser variable on Purchase Decisions is 0.236, indicating that the influence of celebrity endorsers on purchasing decisions is strong or large. This condition is seen when consumers feel that the celebrity who endorses the product has credibility and relevance, they are more likely to make purchasing decisions.

CONCLUSION

Price perception (X1) has a significant effect on Online Customer Review (OCR) in Universitas Riau Gen Z graduate students. This means that a positive price perception will increase online consumer reviews provided by University of Riau Gen Z graduate students.

Celebrity endorser (X2) has a significant effect on OCR in University of Riau Gen Z graduate students. In other words, the use of the right celebrity endorser can increase positive online consumer reviews from University of Riau Gen Z graduate students.

Price perception (X1) has a significant effect on the purchase decision of Skintific products in graduate students of Universitas Riau Gen Z. This shows that the price that is considered in accordance with product quality can strengthen the purchase decision of Skintific products.

Celebrity endorser (X2) has a significant influence on the purchase decision of Skintific products. That is, the presence of credible and attractive celebrity endorsers can improve the purchase decision of Skintific products.

OCR as an intervening variable has a significant effect on the purchase decision of Skintific products. This means that positive online consumer reviews can reinforce the purchasing decisions of Skintific products by University of Riau Gen Z graduate students.

Price perception (X1) through the OCR variable has a significant effect on the purchase decision of Skintific products. That is, a positive price perception, reinforced by good online consumer reviews, can improve the purchase decision of Skintific products.

Celebrity endorser (X2) through the OCR variable has a significant effect on the purchase decision of Skintific products. This shows that effective celebrity endorsers, backed by positive online consumer reviews, can improve purchasing decisions for Skintific products.

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